

Research Article

Clean Drops from the Sky: Rainwater Harvesting and Treatment Project

Ang Lit Jie¹, Meghna², Tee Ya Xuan³, Jong Zheng Quan⁴, Lioe Darren⁵, Lim Le Tao⁶ and Tan Yong Chee^{7,*}

¹ Sekolah Menengah Paragon; 222070005@paragon.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0004-6974-3686
² Sekolah Menengah Paragon; 232080004@paragon.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0004-8203-733X
³ Sekolah Menengah Paragon; 222070019@paragon.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0000-1704-5326
⁴ Sekolah Menengah Paragon; 202050004@paragon.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0007-0911-8207
⁵ Sekolah Menengah Paragon; 222070020@paragon.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0003-3365-6604
⁶ Sekolah Menengah Paragon; 222070040@paragon.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0002-3260-4573
⁷ Sekolah Menengah Paragon; yongchee.tan@paragon.edu.my
* Correspondence: yongchee.tan@paragon.edu.my; 60177491374.

Abstract: Despite high annual rainfall, Malaysia continues to face challenges in water quality and sustainable usage. Rainwater in urban areas is often acidic due to atmospheric pollutants. Thus, this study presents the development and evaluation of a residential rainwater harvesting and filtration system. Two collector models—Model A and Model B—were constructed to assess collection efficiency. Model B, designed with an integrated drainage system, collected 150 cm³ of rainwater in a shorter time, outperforming Model A. To address rainwater acidity, six filtration systems were tested using various ratios of activated carbon and limestone. Water quality parameters, including pH, conductivity, and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), were measured before and after filtration. Initial pH values of collected rainwater ranged from 4.06 to 4.31, confirming its acidic nature. All filtration systems improved pH, with limestone-containing filters demonstrating the most significant changes. The 50:50 combination of activated carbon and limestone (Set 4) was the most effective, raising the pH to a near-neutral level of 7.11 and producing water with a TDS of 136 ppm. Although both conductivity and TDS increased slightly after filtration, all values remained within safe and acceptable limits, improving mineral content and water taste. The system was further tested under real-world conditions in Taman Nilam, Pontian, Johor. Filtered rainwater in this setting showed a pH increase from 6.33 to 7.74, with conductivity and TDS staying below recommended thresholds. These results confirm the system's effectiveness in reducing rainwater acidity while ensuring water remains safe and palatable for household use. This study demonstrates that a rainwater harvesting system with a balanced filtration mix of activated carbon and limestone offers a sustainable, efficient, and practical solution for improving residential water quality in urban environments.

Keywords: Rainwater harvesting; Filtration system; Water quality improvement

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1. INTRODUCTION

Malaysia experiences substantial annual rainfall, yet continues to face significant challenges in water conservation and quality management. Urbanization and climate change have exacerbated water demand and pollution, necessitating the adoption of sustainable water solutions. Studies have shown that rainwater, particularly in urban areas, tends to be more acidic. For example, a 2023 study assessing

ionic species in rainwater across highland and lowland regions in Malaysia analyzed variables such as pH, H^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cl^- , NO_3^- , and SO_4^{2-} . The results indicated a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in Mn^{2+} concentrations between Cameron Highlands (CH) and Petaling Jaya (PJ), with PJ rainfall being more acidic due to higher concentrations of Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , and NO_3^- (Zaini et al., 2023).

In response to these challenges, a rainwater harvesting and treatment system that ensures safe water quality, offers environmental benefits, and utilizes appropriate technologies should be designed. Rainwater harvesting is a key option in adapting to water shortages and future demands, potentially alleviating pressure on existing water resources. This work evaluates a rooftop rainwater harvesting system (RWHS) installed as part of a decentralized wastewater treatment system, designed to enable a circular economy by providing a more reliable water supply (Richards et al., 2021). Using this method, collected rainwater can be utilized in various activities. According to research, a rainwater harvesting system (RHS) was designed for a waste treatment facility to be used for washing vehicles and other equipment, cleaning outdoor concrete or asphalt surfaces, and watering green areas (Fernandes et al., 2015).

Various types of rainwater harvesting systems have been introduced to the market; however, these alternatives have their downsides. Rainwater harvesting (RWH) systems have been in use since ancient times, and their usage has been increasing in recent years. Nevertheless, due to improper planning and design, problems have been observed, leading to polluted collected water. The major causes of water contamination are attributed to the use of toxic materials in the rain harvesting system, faulty operation, inadequate filtration, and improper disinfection methods (Shakya and Thanju, 2013).

In this study, two different rainwater harvesting system models and six types of rainwater filtration systems composed of activated carbon and limestone in varying ratios were introduced. Initially, the optimization of the rainwater collector model was conducted to determine the more effective design for rainwater harvesting. Subsequently, a series of water quality analyses—including pH value, conductivity, and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)—were performed on water samples from the six different filtration systems. Finally, to confirm the system's effectiveness, a real case study was conducted in Taman Nilam, Pontian, Johor, Malaysia. The study found that rainwater harvesting Model B, combined with a filtration system using a 50:50 ratio of activated carbon to limestone, was the most effective. This combination produced cleaner filtered rainwater with a neutral pH of approximately 7.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Optimization of Rainwater Collector Model

Model A

Model B

Figure 1. Rainwater collector models

Two models of rainwater collector systems designed for residential installation were developed, as shown in Figure 1. Model A was constructed using corrugated plastic boards for the

house structure, a filter funnel as the rainwater collector, small PVC pipes for the water transfer system, and a plastic bottle as the water tank. In contrast, Model B utilized corrugated plastic boards for both the house structure and the drainage system, small PVC pipes for water transfer, and a plastic bottle as the water tank. The optimization of the rainwater collector model was conducted by measuring the time taken to collect 150 cm³ of water for each model. The experiment was conducted three times.

2.2 Investigation of Suitable Rainwater Filter System

Figure 2. Six different types of rainwater filters

Six different types of rainwater filters as shown in Figure 2 were introduced in this project. The filters include: a plain sieve, 100% activated carbon, 75% activated carbon with 25% limestone, 50% activated carbon with 50% limestone, 75% limestone with 25% activated carbon, and 100% limestone. Water quality analyses such as the pH value, water conductivity and total dissolved solids (TDS) were conducted using a pH meter RCYAGO 4 in 1 pH/TDS/EC/Temperature Meter Water Quality Monitor Horticulture Water Quality Test Pen. The water used in this study was sourced from tap water.

2.3 Real Sample Study

Rainwater was collected from Taman Nilam, Pontian, Johor, Malaysia. Initially, the rainwater was analyzed using a pH meter, and its pH value, conductivity, and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) were recorded. It was then poured through each filter into separate beakers. After filtration, the resulting filtrates were tested again using a pH meter, and their pH values, conductivity, and TDS levels were recorded.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Optimization of Rainwater Collector Model

Model B took a shorter time to collect 150 cm³ of water compared to Model A. Figure 3 shows the front and top views of both models. From Figure 3, it can be observed that Model B is more effective at collecting rainwater because it includes a drainage system that efficiently directs water into the collector. As a result, Model B is more effective than Model A.

Front View

Top View

Figure 3. Model B

3.2 Water Quality Before and After Filtration

To evaluate the effectiveness of various filtration systems in rainwater harvesting, tests were conducted using different compositions of filter media. The parameters measured include pH, conductivity, and total dissolved solids (TDS) before and after filtration. Table 1 presents summary of the result.

Table 1. The data before and after the experiment

Type of Filter System		pH	Conductivity ($\mu\text{s/cm}$)	TDS (ppm)
Set 1.1	Before	4.06	184	92
Only Sieve	After	4.31	188	95
Set 1.2	Before	4.31	186	93
Only Sieve	After	4.31	186	93
Set 1.3	Before	4.31	188	94
Only Sieve	After	4.31	188	94
Set 2.1	Before	4.22	178	90
100% Carbon	After	5.05	192	96
Set 2.2	Before	4.13	184	93
100% Carbon	After	5.02	184	93
Set 2.3	Before	4.13	184	93
100% Carbon	After	4.74	196	97
Set 3.1	Before	4.22	178	90
75% Carbon 25% Limestone	After	7.13	257	132
Set 3.2	Before	4.22	178	90
75% Carbon 25% Limestone	After	7.47	273	136
Set 3.3	Before	4.22	178	90
75% Carbon 25% Limestone	After	6.96	299	151
Set 4.1	Before	4.19	184	92
50% Carbon 50% Limestone	After	6.49	247	125
Set 4.2	Before	4.19	184	92
50% Carbon 50% Limestone	After	7.11	271	136
Set 4.3	Before	4.19	184	92
50% Carbon 50% Limestone	After	7.2	243	122
Set 5.1	Before	4.19	184	92
25% Carbon 75% Limestone	After	8.12	281	140
Set 5.2	Before	4.19	184	92
25% Carbon 75% Limestone	After	8.2	279	139
Set 5.3	Before	4.19	188	94
25% Carbon 75% Limestone	After	7.46	279	139
Set 6.1	Before	4.19	188	94
100% Limestone	After	6.66	196	98
Set 6.2	Before	4.19	188	94
100% Limestone	After	6.18	209	105
Set 6.3	Before	4.19	188	94
100% Limestone	After	6.25	219	110

Acidic rainwater poses environmental risks by lowering soil pH, leading to nutrient loss and increased availability of toxic heavy metals, which can harm plant growth and damage infrastructure (Singh & Agrawal, 2007). To address this, the introduced filtration systems were designed to raise the pH of rainwater, reducing its acidity and mitigating negative impacts. Post-filtration analysis showed that filters containing limestone significantly improved water quality. Conductivity, an indicator of dissolved ions, increased most in Set 5—from 184 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 279 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ —followed by Sets 3 and 4, while sieve-only and carbon-only filters showed minimal change. All conductivity values remained below the 500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ threshold considered acceptable for drinking water (U.S. EPA, 2012). Similarly, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) levels rose in limestone-based filters, with Set 5.2 reaching 139 ppm, and Sets 4.2 and 3.2 close behind. These values fall within the optimal range of 150–300 mg/L for taste and mineral content, as recommended by WHO and NHMRC (2022), indicating that the filtered rainwater is both safe and palatable. From the results, set 4 was selected as the most suitable rainwater filtration system, as it produced water with a pH close to 7 and appeared almost clean, making it ideal for general use.

3.3 Real Sample Study

To evaluate the effectiveness of filtration system introduced in the project was practical. A real sample study was conducted at Taman Nilam, Pontian, Johor, Malaysia. Figure 4 shows the pH value, water conductivity and TDS of the rainwater before and after filtration.

Figure 4. Water analysis of rainwater before and after filtration

After filtration, the pH value of the rainwater improved significantly from 6.33 to 7.74. Although water conductivity and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) increased following filtration, the results remained well within safe limits—below the 500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ threshold for conductivity and under 300 ppm for TDS. These values fall within the optimal range of 150–300 mg/L recommended by the WHO and NHMRC for palatability and mineral content. These findings indicate that the filtered rainwater not only became less acidic but also gained essential minerals, enhancing both its taste and overall quality

4. DISCUSSION

The study found that Model B was more efficient than Model A in collecting rainwater due to its integrated drainage system. Among the six filtration types tested, filters containing a mix of activated carbon and limestone significantly improved water quality. Set 4 (50% carbon, 50% limestone) was identified as the most suitable filter, producing water with a pH near 7, acceptable conductivity, and TDS levels within the optimal range for drinking. A real sample study confirmed these findings, showing improved pH (from 6.33 to 7.74) and safe conductivity and TDS levels, indicating the filtered rainwater is both safe and palatable.

5. CONCLUSION

The rainwater harvesting model and treatment method presented provide an effective solution for capturing and purifying rainwater that would otherwise go to waste. The system efficiently collects rainwater and significantly improves its quality through filtration. Among the filter combinations tested, the 50:50 mixture of activated carbon and limestone was the most effective, producing clean water with a neutral pH of approximately 7, making it suitable for various practical uses.

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